

Large neutrino experiments can discover sub-GeV dark matter

Filippo Sala
U. Bologna

NuPhys2026

London

8 Jan 2026

Image credit: IceCube/NASA

Credit Super-Kamiokande
Credit KM3NeT

Credit JUNO
Credit IceCube

Proposed title: Dark Sector

Pheno relevant for neutrino exp.

No overlap with other talks

Large neutrino experiments can discover sub-GeV DM
[my title]

I have new results about it

Dark Sectors

Def New dynamics very weakly coupled to SM

Why They exist (DM, neutrinos...)

When First proposed for SUSY breaking ('hidden sectors')

Where?

Dark Sectors

Def New dynamics very weakly coupled to SM

Why They exist (DM, neutrinos...)

When First proposed for SUSY breaking ('hidden sectors')

Where? If dark matter as guideline then:

> 80 orders of magnitude in mass of viable candidates!

Sub-GeV Dark Matter (+ its dark sector)

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Cosmo histories motivate it/exist

Why?

Links easily with many astro questions

Lot of room for new exp. searches

Sub-GeV Dark Matter (+ its dark sector)

Cosmo histories motivate it/exist

Why?

Thermal freeze-out
at small coupling

Hochberg+ 1402.5143

...

ELDERs

Forbidden DM

Kuflik+ 1512.04545

D'Agnolo Ruderman 1505.07107

$$\langle \sigma v \rangle \approx \frac{\alpha^2}{M_{\text{DM}}^2} \quad \langle \sigma v \rangle_{\text{fo}} \approx \frac{1}{(20 \text{ TeV})^2}$$

Sub-GeV Dark Matter (+ its dark sector)

Why?

Links easily with many astro questions

Gravity Waves at PTAs?

Nanograv 2104.13930, ...
Bringmann+ 2306.09411, ...

Small scale troubles of DM?

Boylan-Kolchin 1103.0007,
Tulin Yu 1705.02358, ...

511 keV galactic photons?

Boehm + astro-ph/0309686, ...
... Das+ 2506.00847

Neutrinos from blazars? ...

De Marchi Granelli Nava FS
2412.07861 + 2506.06416 + ...

Sub-GeV Dark Matter (+ its dark sector)

Why?

Links easily with many astro questions **Not true for other masses!**

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Sub-GeV

Why?

its dark sector)

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its dark sector)

@ $M_{DM} \lesssim \text{GeV}$:

PHONON(S)

MIGDAL & brem

...

Sub-GeV

its dark sector)

Why?

Lot of room for new exp. searches

@ $M_{DM} \lesssim \text{GeV}$:

PHONON(S)

MIGDAL & brem

...

But: better understanding needed

MIGDAL widely used DarkSide, XENON, PandaX, SuperCDMS, SENSEI ...

BUT: TH prediction fails in SM! Tested with neutrons off Xenon in Xu+ 2307.12952

High-energy fluxes of sub-GeV DM

High-velocity DM component unavoidably generated by **Cosmic-ray scatterings**

Bringmann Pospelov 1810.10543

Ema FS Sato 1811.00520

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$$M_{\text{DM}} = 10 \text{ MeV}, \quad M_{\text{mediator}} = \text{GeV}, \quad g_{\chi}g_u = g_{\chi}g_d = 0.1$$

High-energy fluxes of sub-GeV DM

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← Also by **Atmospheric Showers**

Alvey+ 1905.05776 , ...

Pascoli FS Xotta in progress

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Also by **Blazars**

Wang Granelli Ullio 2111.13644, ...

Also by ...

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Also by ...

Also by **Solar Upscattering** (but non-relativistic)

An Pospelov Pradler Ritz+ 1708.03642

Emken Kouvaris Nielsen 1709.06573

...

Recoils induced by fast sub-GeV DM

From **Cosmic Rays**, Ema FS Sato 2011.01939

From **Atmosphere**, Pascoli FS Xotta in progress

Recoil Energies > 10 MeV

go to biggest existing detectors!

From **Cosmic Rays**, Ema FS Sato 2011.01939

From **Atmosphere**, Pascoli FS Xotta in progress

(c) 東京大学宇宙線研究所 神岡宇宙素粒子研究施設

Ema FS Sato 2011.01939 CR-upscattered DM, nucleons

Protons with $p_p > 1.07$ GeV emit Cherenkov light, already used for ν 's in Super-K 0901.1645

We repurposed it!

Super-K then did the search!

Super-K 2209.14968

$$\mathcal{L} \supset g_\chi \phi \bar{\chi} \chi + g_q \phi \bar{q} q$$

$$\sigma_{\text{NR}} = C \frac{g_{\chi\phi}^2 g_{u\phi}^2 \mu_{\chi p}^2}{\pi m_\phi^4}$$

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DM direct detection experiments also did

PandaX 2301.03010
LZ 2503.18158,...

Using DM models is necessary

Ema Sala Sato 2011.01939,...

Scalar mediator

$$\mathcal{L} \supset g_\chi \phi \bar{\chi} \chi + g_q \phi \bar{q} q$$

$$m_\phi = 1 \text{ GeV}$$

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To avoid being inconsistent!

No model exists (?) that gives high constant cross sections of fast DM

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Ema Sala Sato 2011.01939,...

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No model exists (?) that gives high constant cross sections of fast DM

To compare with results from DM direct detection

Energy in standard DD is very different

To compare with results from non-DM experiments

colliders, telescopes, ...

Scalar mediator

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$$m_\phi = 1 \text{ GeV}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{NR}} = C \frac{g_{\chi\phi}^2 g_{u\phi}^2 \mu_{\chi p}^2}{\pi m_\phi^4}$$

To look for EW invariant completion

Status in a given model (w/o fast DM)

Standard low-threshold DD (SENSEI,...), current limits

$$\mathcal{L} \supset g_\chi \phi \bar{\chi} \chi + g_q \phi \bar{q} q$$

$$m_\phi = 1 \text{ GeV}$$

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Meson decays
(Very depend on coupling structure)

..., Cox Dolan Ghosh
2512.20825

Atmospheric DM: status

Alvey+ 1905.05776,
Arguelles+ 2022,...

All studies (that I know of) had mediator lighter than $O(100)$ MeV decaying into DM

Excluded by accelerators and stars!

Batell+ 1812.05103

Atmospheric DM

Pascoli FS Xotta in progress

1. Use heavy mediators
2. Use neutrino detectors

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These ideas **test also inelastic DM** unlike 'standard' direct detection

see e.g. [Bell+ 2108.00583](#)

Atmospheric DM

Pascoli FS Xotta in progress

1. Use heavy mediators
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Experimentalist
in Super-K, JUNO, DUNE,...

Largest ν experiments and sub-GeV DM?

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Can IceCube (&KM3NeT) detect high-energy DM fluxes?

Cavicchi De Wasseige Lamoreux Mauro FS
PoS ICRC2025 (2025) 475 + In progress

Room for new ideas!

Twist: can some of their highest-E ν 's be due to **sub-GeV DM**?

De Marchi Granelli Nava FS
2412.07861
2506.06416
2507.12278

Largest ν experiments and sub-GeV DM?

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Yes! So far using baseline ELOWEN and GRECO elections

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Largest ν experiments and sub-GeV DM?

For more see Andrea De Marchi's talk (yesterday...)

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Photons observed from many blazars over many energies

Neutrinos first detected in 2017 by IceCube from TXS 0506+056

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FILIPPO SALA (U. BOLOGNA)

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Problem: find jet model that explain all observations

'Leptohadronic single-zone' models: leptons&protons in jet

They fail for IceCube

Cerruti+ 1807.04335
Keivani+ 1807.04537
...

Blazars

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For more see Aditya Tamar's talk (this morning...)

blazars over many energies
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Protons break and produce ν from π^\pm

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Explains ν detected from TXS 0506+056...

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Explains ν detected from TXS 0506+056...

...OK with all other DM limits & for conservative DM spike

Take-home: **Fast DM** + **Neutrino Detectors** =

Credit Super-Kamiokande
Credit KM3NeT

Credit JUNO
Credit IceCube

Fast DM is generic.

Neutrino Detectors exist.

Back up

More on: [511 keV galactic photons](#)

An example: 511 keV line

Problem
where are the e^+ from??

COSI balloon 1912.00110

Figure 10. Positron annihilation spectrum from the 2016 COSI flight from a 16° source region around the GC. The spectrum is fit with a single Gaussian component to describe the 511 keV line and the theoretical o-Ps continuum spectrum. The total number of counts in the 511 keV line is 2560 ± 300 cts. The detection significance is 7.2σ detection.

Line observed since the 70's (INTEGRAL,...)

Origin: $e^+ e^-$ annihilations & bound states

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From astrophysics?

Low-mass X-ray binaries?

Bartels Calore Storm Weniger 1803.04370

Neutron Star Mergers?

Fuller Kusenko Radice Takhistov 1811.00133

... see review Siegert 2303.15582

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- ... see review Siegert 2303.15582

First explored in Bohem+ astro-ph/0309686

From dark matter annihilations?

$\langle \sigma v \rangle_{511} \simeq 5 \cdot 10^{-31} \left(\frac{M_{\text{DM}}}{3 \text{ MeV}} \right)^2 \frac{\text{cm}^3}{\text{sec}} \longrightarrow \text{Equilibrium with SM in Early Uni}$

Yes if:

- Vincent+ 1201.0997 (NFW DM profile)
- DM mass $\lesssim 3 \text{ MeV}$
- Beacom Yuksel astro-ph/0512411

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DM mass $\lesssim 3 \text{ MeV}$

Beacom Yuksel astro-ph/0512411

Equilibrium with SM in Early Uni

↓

Excluded by BBN + CMB

Wilkinson Vincent Boehm McCabe 1602.01114

Sub-GeV DM can explain the 511 keV line

DM at 3 MeV OK with cosmo if it also annihilates into neutrinos Escudero 1812.05605, Sabti+ 1910.01649
(no 511 keV line here)

Ema FS Sato 2007.08440 DM models for 511 keV line, with rich pheno

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Idea: what if we include DM spike in GC?

De La Torre Luque Balaji Fairbairn FS Silk 2410.16379

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Lower $\langle\sigma v\rangle_{511}$ explains the excess

$M_{\text{DM}} \gtrsim 10 \text{ MeV}$ works! Much easier to build DM models!

See also Siegert+ 2506.00847

More on: [DM-electron scatterings](#)

Sub-GeV DM coupled with electrons?

Light mediators: different interplay of searches, different cosmo **not in this talk**

Blazar ν 's from sub-GeV dark matter

De Marchi Granelli Nava 2412.07861

OK cool, but does it work on the DM side?